

HOT GAS TEMPERATURE EFFECT ON THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES THERMAL USING THE AUTOMATED TAPE LAYING

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ABSTRACT

The effect of hot gas temperature on the thermal field and heat flux of the thermoplastic composites produced by the automated tape laying process was simulated and estimated based on different laying speeds, which was conducted with the self-developed simulation program based on ANSYS software. The hot gas temperature of 400, 500, 600 and 700 °C were studied and the simulation results present that the non-uniform of the thermal field distribution of the thermoplastic composite increasing as the hot gas temperature increases. The thermal distribution of the laminates of the thickness direction adjacent to the mandrel shows the maximum temperature value.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced composites have widely concerns in aerospace field for the advantages of high specific strength, modulus, corrosion resistance properties, which consists of the thermoset and thermoplastic composites. The thermoset composites have widely used in the aircraft field due to its mechanisms have well understood by the researchers. However, the high produce cost, harshly low temperature storage requirements and brittleness features hinder its further application under the of impact load service [1-3]. The thermoplastic composite structures are recently used dramatically in the civil aircraft for its forming ability and fracture toughness. The critical factor of the thermoplastic composites in order to achieve the more widely used is to lower its cost, and the automated tape laying (ATL) process has regarded as a cost-effective method in producing the composites.

In the ATL process, the prepreg material viscosity and laying process of the thermoplastic prepreg was strikingly affected by the thermal history and distribution in the process. Of particular importance is how these factors influence the thermoplastic composite thermal field in the laying process. The effects of these factors are commonly studied with the testing method by using the sensors, which usually results the expensively research process and difficult to adopt the control variables method to study the potential effects of the concerns influence factors.

In this study, the effect of the hot gas temperature on the thermal field of the thermoplastic laminates in ATL process is studied with the transient thermal analysis and the simulated results of the distributions of thermal field and thermal flux are estimated with the results of studied hot-gas temperature, respectively.

2 THEORETICAL PRINCIPLE AND MATERIALS

2.1 Theoretical principle

Some assumptions were adopted in the analyses, which were composed of: (1) the fiber bundles of the thermoplastic prepreg were neatly laid on the mould surface and were well infiltrated by the thermoplastic resin; (2) the properties differences of the fiber fabric and matrix through the thickness direction can be ignored due to the thickness of the thermoplastic laminates is small enough; (3) the laminates are laid along the single direction. The simulation process is conducted with the assumption of the laminates having the isotropic material. The heat transfer in the laying process is regarded as the one dimensional through the thickness direction and abided by the heat transfer equation [4-5].

$$k \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} = \rho C \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

Here, k is the thermal conductivity, ρ and C are the density and specific heat capacity. The thermal distribution in the layup processes are studied on the transient analysis based on the death-birth element method. The temperature distributions in the laying process were also affected by the heat gas temperature for the finite thermal conductivity of the “new” prepreg layer.

2.2 Introduction of automated laying process

The prepreg laying processes of the ATL process is shown in Fig. 1, in which the prepreg layers are increased by layer and layer along the thickness direction under the hot-gas and roller load.

Figure 1: Layup pattern of the thermoplastic composites of the ATL process

Figure 2: Flow chart of the transient thermal analysis adopted in present study

The thermal field distribution of the thermoplastic laminates in the ATL process are simulated based on the self-compiled simulation program based on the software of ANSYS with APDL language, which is composed of the modules of pre-process, solution and post-process [6-7] (Fig. 2). The laminates contain of six prepreg layers with the single layer thickness of 0.188 mm. The laminate

length is 60 mm and the stress field was respectively studied with the hot-gas temperature of 400 °C, 500 °C, 600 °C and 700 °C at 10 mm/s. This laying rate was decided on our previous study, in which the effect of laying rates of 20 mm/s, 15 mm/s, 10 mm/s, and 5 mm/s were respectively studied and the higher laying rate prone to cause the uneven distribution of the thermal field, although it has important significance to improve the production efficiency. It is also worth pointing out that hot gas temperature will affect the crystallinity of the thermoplastic matrix, moreover, the slower laying rate is unfavorable to increase the production efficiency.

The detailed thermoplastic prepreg properties and the boundary conditions of the studied model used in the simulation are presented in the Table 1 [8-9]. Effect of the hot gas temperature on the thermal field distribution during the layup processes are studied based on the transient increment analysis method. The temperature distributions of the thermal field and heat flux of the thermoplastic laminates were strikingly affected by the hot gas temperature. The suitable hot gas temperature can be improved the laying performance of the thermoplastic prepreg and keep the uniform distribution of the crystallinity of the thermoplastic laminate. Physical properties of the thermoplastic composites prepreg under the different temperature are shown in Table 2.

Figure 3: Detailed flow process diagram of the transient thermal field analysis used in this study

Classification	Detailed items	Value
Geometry models information	Single layer prepreg thickness [mm]	0.188
	Laminate length [mm]	50
	Layer number of the laminates [mm]	6
	Mandrel thickness [mm]	8
Thermal properties of the studied laminates	Axial thermal conductivity K_x [W/m°C]	6.5
	Transverse thermal conductivity K_y [W/m°C]	0.65
	Density (ρ) [kg/m ³]	1562
Thermal properties of the mandrel material	Heat capacity c [J/kg°C]	1425
	thermal conductivity k [W/m°C]	237
	Density (ρ) [kg/m ³]	2700

	Heat capacity c [J/kg $^{\circ}$ C]	905
Boundary conditions	Convective heat-transfer coefficient of the mandrel under the natural condition h [W/m 2 $^{\circ}$ C]	13
	Convective heat-transfer coefficient of the laminates under the heat gas condition h [W/m 2 $^{\circ}$ C]	25
	Environmental temperature T_{∞} ($^{\circ}$ C)	20
	Initial temperature T_0 ($^{\circ}$ C)	20

Table 1: Properties parameters and the boundary conditions of the simulation models^[7]

T/ $^{\circ}$ C	K/(W/m K)		C/(W/m K)
	K(x)/	K(y)	
0	6	0.6	800
60	6.5	0.65	908
120	7	0.7	1016
180	7.5	0.75	1124
240	8	0.8	1232
300	8.5	0.85	1340
360	9	0.9	2080
390	9.25	0.95	1660
420	9.5	0.9	1663
480	10	0.9	1664

Table2: Thermal conductivity and specific heat capacity properties of the thermoplastic composites

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The hot gas temperature presents an important effect on the thermal field based on the simulation results of the laying rate of 10mm/s. Distributions of thermal field and heat flux distribution along and vertical to the fiber direction of the model under the hot gas temperature of 400 $^{\circ}$ C are given in Figs. 4(a) and 4(b) respectively, which have a feature of symmetry distribution for the composite laminate's geometric symmetry. The central parts of thermoplastic composites have the highest temperature and present the concentric ring form distribution from the laid layer to the 'new' layers along the thickness direction. The thermoplastic composites are laid from the left to right along the transverse direction; it can see that temperature of the two corners of the thermoplastic laminates have the relatively low for it is the lateral component and has the comparable good convection boundary conditions. It is more or less inevitable that the non-uniform temperature distribution in the automatic laying process; however, it has found that too high temperature of the central parts leads to uneven distribution of crystallinity and affect the final mechanical property.

The simulation results of the thermal field and heat flux distribution along and vertical to the fiber direction of the studied model at the laying rate of 10 mm/s under the hot gas temperature of 500 $^{\circ}$ C are respectively shown in the Figs. 4(c) and 4(d). It has a similar trend with the results at the 400 $^{\circ}$ C, as well as the heat flux distributions for both temperature cases. However, the temperature of the central component non-uniformity increases with the increase of the hot gas temperature. In addition, the simulation results of the thermal field and heat flux distributions of the model for the hot gas temperature of 600 $^{\circ}$ C are presented in Figs. 5(a) and 5(b), respectively. The corresponding simulation results of thermal field and heat flux for the studied model under the hot gas temperature of 700 $^{\circ}$ C are respectively shown in the Figs. 5(c) and 5(d). The non-uniformities of thermal field of thermoplastic composites has a further increasing trend as the hot gas temperature increases. The thermal distribution of the laminates of the thickness direction have the maximum values, and the prepreg layers adjacent

to the mandrel show the maximum temperature value, which caused by the heat released during crystallization and the heat transfer of the mandrel materials.

Figure 4: thermal field (left) and heat flux (right) distribution of the hot-gas temperature of the thermoplastic composite: (a) and (b) are the temperature of 400 °C; (c) and (d) are the temperature of 500°C, respectively

Figure 5: thermal field (left) and heat flux (right) distribution of the hot-gas temperature of the thermoplastic composite: (a) and (b) are the temperature of 600 °C; (c) and (d) are the temperature of 700°C, respectively

The following points can be concluded with the simulation results of different hot gas temperature at the laying rate of 10 mm/s, which are composed of: (1) the gradients of the thermal field and heat flux of the thermoplastic laminate increases as the hot gas temperature increasing in the ATL process; (2) the thermal fields illustrate and the central part of the thermoplastic composites has the comparable high temperature for the crystallinity release heat and heat transfer of the mandrel tool; (3) the non-uniformity distribution of the thermal field is comparison small for the small hot gas temperature and the non-uniformity shows obviously increases as the hot gas temperature increasing, which was caused by the heat distribution between the thermoplastic prepreg layers cannot be timely and effectively released due to its limited thermal conductivity property.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Effects of the hot-gas temperature on the thermal field distribution of the thermoplastic composites by using the automated tape laying (ATL) process were studied based on the simulation method in this study. Four kinds of the hot gas temperature of 400, 500, 600 and 700 °C were adopted to analysis its effects on the distributions of thermal field and heat flux of the thermoplastic composites. The results show the hot-gas temperature presents an important effect on the thermal field and heat flux of the thermoplastic composites; Moreover, a comparable small hot-gas temperature is beneficial to obtain a uniform thermal field. The gradient of the thermal increases as the increasing of hot-gas temperature and will compromise the final mechanical property of thermoplastic composites.

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